

Educator Survey Questionnaire

1. If you agree to participate, check all the boxes below.
 - a. I am age 18 or older, I have read this consent form or had it read to me
 - b. I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study and I want to continue to the survey
 - c. I have experience in using personal devices or personally-obtained software applications for teaching and research activities
2. Please enter your Prolific Id
3. Please select the type of the institute you teach
 - a. K-12
 - b. HEI
4. Please list 3-5 personal applications you have used for teaching, grading, or research-related tasks FOR EACH APP LISTED
 - a. Why did you choose [APP]?
 - b. List 2-3 most important factors you considered when selecting [APP].
 - c. How did you learn about [APP]?
 - d. Did you integrate [APP] to other institutionally licensed tools (such as Canvas or Zoom)? YES/NO/MAYBE
 - e. Did students have to register with [APP] using their institutional credentials (e.g., email or id)? YES/NO/MAYBE
 - f. Was there an alternative to [APP] available within the university's tool profile? If yes, why did you choose not to use it?

- g. Is [APP] still in use? YES/NO
- h. (optional) Did you transfer the data that [APP] collected to another tool or to back up data? If yes, Please briefly explain the transfer process.
- i. (optional) Did [APP] provide an option to request deletion of data before discontinuing? YES/NO/UNSURE
- j. (optional) Did you use the data deletion feature for [APP]? YES/NO/UNSURE
- k. (optional) Why you did not use the data deletion feature for [APP]?
YES/NO/UNSURE
- l. Did you consider any security or privacy concerns when choosing and using [APP]?
- m. Have you reported or observed any security or privacy issues with [APP]?
- n. Does [APP] access any data that you consider may violate the privacy of the data subject/owner?
- o. To your knowledge, does [APP] share any data it collects with advertisers or other third parties?
- p. Was [APP] compliant with FERPA (Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act)?
YES/NO/MAYBE/N/A
- q. Was [APP] compliant with HIPAA (Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act)? YES/NO/MAYBE/N/A
- r. Please rate the following statements regarding [APP] on a 5-point scale from Strongly agree to Strongly disagree:
 - i. I trust this tool/application to keep user data private.

- ii. This tool/application is competent in safeguarding personal data.

PERSONAL DEVICE USE:

5. Have you ever used your personal mobile phone or computer for teaching or grading purposes? (optional) If no, why not?
6. How frequently do you use your personal device (e.g., laptop, tablet, smartphone) for teaching-related tasks?
7. Have you ever downloaded any academic documents (e.g., a grade sheet) to your personal device? - Grade Sheets
8. Have you ever downloaded any academic documents (e.g., a grade sheet) to your personal device? - Student's Work
9. Have you ever downloaded any academic documents (e.g., a grade sheet) to your personal device? - Student data
10. Have you ever downloaded any academic documents (e.g., a grade sheet) to your personal device? - Other Documents (please explain)
11. Does that personal device have automatic cloud backup enabled through your personal account?
12. INSTITUTIONAL POLICY and GENERAL APP-RELATED CONCERNS:
 - a. Are you aware of any institutional policies regarding the use of non-institutionally acquired tools for educational purposes?
 - b. What are the institutional policies you are aware of? Please provide descriptions (or links if available).

- c. Has your institution ever reported/warned about any risk (such as a data breach) related to the use of independently acquired apps or devices?
- d. Did you change a behavior based on it? If so, what was it?
- e. Did you ever refrain from installing an app due to unusual permissions?
- f. Did you ever refrain from installing an app because it asked for a large number of permissions compared to the features provided?
- g. Did you ever refrain from installing an app because it asked for a large number of permissions compared to the features provided?
- h. Did you ever uninstall an app, after you heard that it is privacy-intrusive?
- i. How did the app invade privacy? (open-ended)

13. DIGITAL SECURITY AND PRIVACY BEHAVIOR - Please rate the following statements regarding [APP] on a 5-point scale from Strongly agree to Strongly disagree:

- a. I use a password/passcode to unlock my laptop or tablet.
- b. If I discover a security problem, I continue what I was doing because I assume someone else will fix it.
- c. I submit information to websites without first verifying that it will be sent securely.
- d. I try to make sure that the programs I use in personal devices are up-to-date.
- e. It is important for me to protect other people's privacy even when it is difficult to do so.
- f. Other people's privacy is valuable to me.
- g. It is important to protect other people's privacy even if I need to invest time and effort to do it.

- h. I am concerned that mobile apps may use my personal information for other purposes without notifying me or getting my authorization.
- i. When I give personal information to use mobile apps, I am concerned that apps may use my information for other purposes.
- j. I am concerned that mobile apps may share my personal information with other entities without getting my authorization.

DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONS:

- 14. Please select your gender.
- 15. Please select your highest level of education.
- 16. Please enter your academic discipline (e.g., Computer Science, Sociology, Accounting)
- 17. Please enter your years of experience as an educator/instructor.
- 18. Do you have any other comments regarding this study? At the end of your answer append the following sentence: ``No more comments''